

A green approach for the synthesis of biologically active heterocyclic compounds at the platinum electrode

Sanjeev Kumar^{a*} and H. N. Srivastava

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Iswar Saran Degree College (University of Allahabad), Allahabad-211 004, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : sanjivks77@gmail.com Fax : 91-532-2544578

Department of Zoology, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 03 March 2011, revised 10 may 2012, accepted 01 August 2012

Abstract : In the present study, 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (4a-k) have been synthesized by the electrochemical oxidation of semicarbazone (3a-k) using platinum anode at room temperature under controlled potential electrolysis in an undivided cell assembly. Two platinum electrodes in the form of square plates were used as working as well as counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode. The structure of the compounds was confirmed by different techniques i.e. IR, NMR, mass spectral and elemental analyses. The antibacterial activity of the derivatives was also assessed and compared with the parent against a series of Gram-positive *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli* and Gram-negative bacteria *Streptococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*. The antifungal activity was assessed against the fungal strain *Aspergillus niger*, *Cryosporium pannical*, *Pellicularia solmanicolor* and *Candida albicans* and compared against the standard antifungal drug Griseovulvin. All compounds exhibit significant antibacterial activity and antifungal activity.

Keywords : Electrochemical oxidation, controlled potential, 1,3,4-oxadiazole, semicarbazone, antimicrobial agents.

Introduction

The development of eco-friendly synthetic methods in the field of synthetic organic chemistry has a great importance. In context of green chemistry, a series of 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (4) have been synthesized by electrooxidative cyclization of semicarbazone (3) as a new general environmentally benign synthetic method. In this respect, organic synthesis involving multi-component reactions under reagents free conditions is a basic protocol because multistep conventional synthesis produces considerable amounts of environmentally unfavorable wastes, mainly due to a series of complex isolation procedures often involving expensive, toxic and hazardous solvents and reagents after each step¹⁻⁶. The application of electricity as a non-conventional energy source for activation of reactions in the suitable solvents has now gained popularity over the usual homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions, as it provides chemical processes with special attributes, such as enhanced reaction rates, better selectivity, higher yield of pure products and sev-

eral eco-friendly advantages⁷⁻⁹. These reactions do not require oxidizing reagents and can be performed at ordinary room temperature.

1,3,4-Oxadiazoles have been shown to possess diverse biological activities such as antibacterial^{10,11}, anti-HIV¹⁰, antifungal¹²⁻¹⁴, genotoxic¹², antitubercular¹⁵, virucidal¹⁶, antimalarial^{17,18}, insecticidal¹⁹, herbicidal²⁰, analgesic²¹, anti-inflammatory²², muscle relaxants²³, anticonvulsant²⁴, sedative, hypnotic²⁵, anticancer²⁶ and lipid peroxidation inhibitor²⁷.

The conventional methods of synthesis including bromine oxidation of semicarbazide derivatives¹ and the cyclodesulfurisation of acylthiosemicarbazide derivatives in the solution using I₂/NaOH or 1,3-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC)^{2,3} as well as mercury(II) acetate [Hg(OAc)₂] or yellow mercury(II) oxide HgO⁴⁻⁶ require hazardous and toxic reagents. Recently, Evans²⁸ have prepared 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles by rapid parallel synthesis using resin-bound reagents. All these methods are usually carried out in various different syn-

thetic steps and require heating at high temperature. Each stage of the reaction including extraction and purification of the products from the mixture requires great precautions. The present electrochemical technique is superior in comparison to the existing methods because this is a single step process and does not require a reagent. It takes place at the surface of electrode via the electron transfer. Thus the electrochemical techniques are perfectly suited for syntheses, and are finding increasing use in discovery processes for new drugs and agrochemicals because of their merits²⁹⁻³¹.

Results and discussion

Considering the importance of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, a series of 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**4**) have synthesized by electrooxidative cyclization of semicarbazone (**3**) as a new general environmentally benign synthetic method in which the use of aforementioned reagents could be minimized in using the quantity and number of chemical reagents. This electrooxidative cyclization gives the oxadiazoles (Scheme 1) without requirement of any hazardous reagents.

Scheme 1. Synthetic route for the preparation of 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles.

Mechanistic proposal : The first step as shown in Scheme 2 represents the deprotonation of **3** to form an anion **3a**, which remains in resonance with its canonical structure **3b** and evolves a free radical **3c** after one electron oxidation. Subsequent second electron oxidation from the free radical **3c** gives a carbocation **3d**. The formation of carbon oxygen bond completes the ring. On losing a proton in the last step 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole (**4**) is obtained.

Novel 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been synthesized in excellent yields using the synthetic route outlined in Schemes 1 and 2. IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectral data are in agreement with the proposed structures of all synthesized compounds. Lack

Scheme 2. Mechanistic proposal.

of ¹H NMR resonances observed with NH and NH₂ functions in the ¹H NMR spectrum of **4a-m** proved that ring closure starting from **3e** resulted in the formation of 2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole ring. This was further substantiated by the ¹³C NMR data of **1** which showed the peaks at δ 170.4-173.4 and 147.5-150.6 due to C₂ and C₅ of oxadiazole respectively. The IR spectrum shows 1600-1623 cm⁻¹ for (C=N-N=C) and 1060-1073 cm⁻¹ for (C-O-C) in the compounds **4a-m** which confirmed the synthesis of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles.

On the analysis of yield it has been observed that when substituents are electron releasing groups, the yields of **4** was marginally higher than that with the electron withdrawing groups at the position 5 in lesser time. However, the aryl groups afforded general yields. Approximately 5-6 F mol⁻¹ of electricity was passed for the electrolysis which is very small in comparison to energy used in other conventional methods.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open glass capillary tube and were uncorrected. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX 300 FT spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal reference. Chemical shifts are on parts per million (ppm) relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. Microanalyses were carried out in the Elementar Vario EL III instrument. IR spectra in KBr were recorded

Note

on a Shimadzu FTIR 8201 PC IR spectrophotometer (4000–400 cm^{-1}). All chemicals used were reagent grade. Silica gel-G₆₀ was used for TLC.

Synthesis of 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles derivatives (4a-m) (General procedure) : Semicarbazide hydrochloride **2** (13.33 mmol) and sodium acetate (12.19 mmol) was dissolved in water (10 mL) then an aldehyde **1** (4.6 mmol) was added with continuous stirring. The mixture was left overnight, which gives semicarbazone **3**. Thoroughly mixed **3** (12.0 mmol) and lithium perchlorate (3.0 mmol) in acetic acid (100 mL) were taken in 250 mL three-electrode cell assembly with platinum plate as working as well as counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. Controlled potential electrolysis^{29–34} was performed (25 °C) at their corresponding oxidation potential and completed in 3 to 5 h. The current potential data was recorded with potentiostat (Table 1). Magnetic stirrer was used for the diffusion of product from the electrode and proper mix-

tetrachloride was further diluted with the excess amount of water and separate out the carbon tetrachloride layer. This extraction process is repeated twice or thrice after which the carbon tetrachloride layer have only product, no more acetic acid. The product was separate out from the carbon tetrachloride layer with the help of rotatory evaporator. Purification by silica gel chromatography afforded **4** in excellent yield.

Analytical and spectral characterization data :

2-Amino-5-(2-methylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4a) : Yellow needles, m.p. 82–83 °C, mol. wt. 173.2; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3444 (NH), 3065 (ArC–H), 3010 (C–H), 2927, 1600 (C=N–N=C), 1430 (C=C), 1265, 1068 (C–O–C), 815, 795 (subs. aromatic); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.75–7.87 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.17 (1H, s, NH), 1.12 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 170.5 (OxadiazC₂), 149.5 (OxadiazC₃), 141.5 (Ar-C₁), 136.0 (Ar-C₂), 129.3 (Ar-C₃), 126.8 (Ar-C₄), 126.7 (Ar-C₆), 125.8 (Ar-C₅), 21.18 (CH₃); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 173

Table 1. Electroorganic synthesis of 5-substituted-2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

Entry	5-(R)	Time (h)	Product	Applied potential (V)	Current (A)	Yield ^a (%)
1	2-MeC ₆ H ₄	3	4a	1.95	0.25	87
2	3-(COOH)C ₆ H ₄	5	4b	1.70	0.20	78
3	2-Pyridinyl	3	4c	1.85	0.13	85
4	3-(4-ClC ₆ H ₄ O)C ₆ H ₄	4	4d	1.70	0.16	90
5	3-(3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ O)C ₆ H ₄	4	4e	1.95	0.17	91
6	3-(3,5-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ O)C ₆ H ₄	4	4f	2.00	0.19	89
7	2,4-(OH) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	3	4g	1.86	0.14	86
8	4-Cl, 3-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₃	5	4h	2.20	0.17	74
9	5-(AcOCH ₂), 2-furyl	4	4i	1.75	0.18	82
10	4-(C ₆ H ₅ CO), 3-(OMe)C ₆ H ₃	4	4j	1.85	0.13	84
11	2,6-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	5	4k	2.00	0.15	72
12	3,5-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	4	4l	1.80	0.20	81
13	5-Br, 4,6-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₂	3	4m	1.15	0.17	88

^aYield of isolated and purified product after column chromatography.

ing of reaction mixture. The reaction mixture containing product was diluted with the distilled water (200 mL) and add carbon tetrachloride or non aqueous solvents (5 mL) and shake the mixture vigorously. The carbon tetrachloride layer containing compound in the bottom and water containing acetic acid layer at the top were obtained. The bottom layer of carbon tetrachloride which have slight amount of acetic acid also was separate out. This carbon

(Found : C, 62.15; H, 3.98; N, 23.91. Calcd. for C₉H₇N₃O : C, 62.42; H, 4.04; N, 24.27%).

2-Amino-5-(3-carboxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4b) : Brown needles, m.p. 89–90 °C, mol. wt. 205.2; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3360 (NH), 3300, 3065 (ArC–H), 1715, 1608 (C=N–N=C), 1430 (C=C), 1280, 1065 (C–O–C), 962, 826, 795 (subs. aromatic); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 12.0 (1H, s, COOH), 8.78 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.17

(1H, s, NH), 7.31–7.51 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.5 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 172.2 (COOH), 171.9 (OxadiaC₂), 148.8 (OxadiaC₅), 141.0 (Ar-C₁), 131.3 (Ar-C₃), 131.0 (Ar-C₆), 128.3 (Ar-C₂), 128.2 (Ar-C₄), 115.5 (Ar-C₅); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 205 (Found : C, 52.25; H, 3.29; N, 20.11. Calcd. for C₉H₇N₃O₃ : C, 52.68; H, 3.41; N, 20.48%).

2-Amino-5-(2-pyridinyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4c) : Yellow needles, m.p. 82–83 °C, mol. wt. 162.2; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3330 (NH), 3065 (PyC-H), 1610 (C=N-N=C), 1430 (C=C), 1063 (C-O-C); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 7.75 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.25–7.69 (4H, m, Py-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 171.4 (OxadiaC₂), 149.7 (OxadiaC₅), 162.3, 150.9, 136.5, 122.8, 123.5 (C_{Py}); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 162 (Found : C, 51.53; H, 3.55; N, 34.40. Calcd. for C₇H₆N₄O : C, 51.85; H, 3.70; N, 34.56%).

2-Amino-5-(3-(4-chlorophenoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4d) : Yellow needles, m.p. 94–96 °C, mol. wt. 287.7; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3330 (NH), 3065 (ArC-H), 1615 (C=N-N=C), 1430 (C=C), 1230 (Ar-O-Ar), 1067 (C-O-C), 832, 788 (subs. aromatic), 730 (Ar-Cl); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 8.75 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.17 (1H, s, NH), 7.31–7.51 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.98 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.75 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 173.4 (OxadiaC₂), 158.3 (Ar-C₄), 157.9 (Ar-C'₁), 150.6 (OxadiaC₅), 132.9 (Ar-C₁), 130.2 (Ar-C'₅), 129.7 (Ar-C'₃), 127.7 (Ar-C₆), 127.7 (Ar-C₂), 127.2 (Ar-C'₄), 115.8 (Ar-C'₆), 115.1 (Ar-C'₂), 114.3 (Ar-C₃), 114.0 (Ar-C₅); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 287.5 (Found : C, 58.19; H, 3.22; N, 14.30; Cl, 12.08. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₀N₃O₂Cl : C, 58.43; H, 3.47; N, 14.60; Cl, 12.34%).

2-Amino-5-(3-(3,4-dichlorophenoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4e) : Brown needles, m.p. 110–111 °C, mol. wt. 322.2; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3315 (NH), 3045 (ArC-H), 1607 (C=N-N=C), 1432 (C=C), 1070 (C-O-C), 842, 796 (subs. aromatic), 731 (Ar-Cl); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 8.76 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.52–7.14 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.96 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.72 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 170.4 (OxadiaC₂), 158.6 (Ar-C'₁), 158.5 (Ar-C₄), 149.8 (OxadiaC₅), 135.9 (Ar-C'₃), 132.5 (Ar-C₁), 130.7 (Ar-C'₅), 127.7 (Ar-C₆), 127.7 (Ar-C₂), 127.3 (Ar-

C'₂), 127.2 (Ar-C'₄), 114.8 (Ar-C'₆), 114.5 (Ar-C₃), 114.4 (Ar-C₅); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 322 (Found : C, 51.68; H, 2.59; N, 12.69; Cl, 21.72. Calcd. for C₁₄H₉N₃O₂Cl : C, 52.17; H, 2.79; N, 13.04; Cl, 22.04%).

2-Amino-5-(3-(3,5-dichlorophenoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4f) : Dark yellow needles, m.p. 115–116 °C, mol. wt. 322.2; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3330 (NH), 3065 (ArC-H), 1609 (C=N-N=C), 1430 (C=C), 1062 (C-O-C), 837, 787 (subs. aromatic), 733 (Ar-Cl); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 8.77 (3H, s, Ar-H), 8.17 (1H, s, NH), 6.85–7.52 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.75 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 172.6 (OxadiaC₂), 161.9 (Ar-C'₁), 158.3 (Ar-C₄), 150.4 (OxadiaC₅), 136.9 (Ar-C'₃), 136.9 (Ar-C'₅), 132.9 (Ar-C₁), 127.7 (Ar-C₆), 127.7 (Ar-C₂), 124.9 (Ar-C'₆), 124.9 (Ar-C'₂), 121.2 (Ar-C'₄), 114.0 (Ar-C₅), 114.3 (Ar-C₃); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 322 (Found : C, 51.68; H, 2.59; N, 12.69; Cl, 21.72. Calcd. for C₁₄H₉N₃O₂Cl : C, 52.17; H, 2.79; N, 13.04; Cl, 22.04%).

2-Amino-5-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4g) : Brown needles, m.p. 75–77 °C, mol. wt. 281.2; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3444 (O-H), 3315 (NH), 3045 (ArC-H), 1607 (C=N-N=C), 1432 (C=C), 1072 (C-O-C), 818, 795 (subs. aromatic); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 8.70 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.17 (1H, s, NH), 6.98 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.09 (1H, s, OH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 173.2 (OxadiaC₂), 155.1 (Ar-C₄), 154.9 (Ar-C₂), 147.6 (OxadiaC₅), 129.9 (Ar-C₆), 120.6 (Ar-C₁), 108.5 (Ar-C₅), 103.0 (Ar-C₃); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 281 (Found : C, 49.10; H, 4.08; N, 21.48. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅NO₅ : C, 49.48; H, 4.12; N, 21.63%).

2-Amino-5-(4-chloro-3-nitro)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4h) : Dark yellow needles, m.p. 80–82 °C, mol. wt. 226.2; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3341 (NH), 3035 (ArC-H), 1620 (C=N-N=C), 1583 (Ar-NO₂), 1430 (C=C), 1062 (C-O-C), 815, 750 (subs. aromatic), 735 (Ar-Cl); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 8.69 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.92 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 170.7 (OxadiaC₂), 149.6 (OxadiaC₅), 148.1 (Ar-C₃), 139.6 (Ar-C₁), 133.7 (Ar-C₆), 129.5 (Ar-C₅), 122.4 (Ar-C₂), 121.6 (Ar-C₄); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 226 (Found : C, 42.21; H, 2.09; N, 24.48; Cl, 15.40. Calcd. for C₈H₅N₄O₃Cl : C, 42.47; H, 2.21; N, 24.77; Cl, 15.70%).

2-Amino-5-(2-(5-acetoxymethyl)furyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4i): Pale yellow needles, m.p. 78–79 °C, mol. wt. 223.2; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 3330 (NH), 3070 (ArC–H), 2855 (alipC–H), 1720 (C=O), 1623 (C=N–N=C), 1435 (C=C), 1285, 1065 (C–O–C); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 7.75 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.29–7.34 (3H, m, Furan-H), 4.20 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 171.3 (Oxadiazole C₂), 170.3 (COO), 150.2 (Oxadiazole C₅), 142.5 (Fur–C₅), 138.6 (Fur–C₂), 113.5 (Fur–C₂), 108.5 (Fur–C₄), 60 (CH₂), 20.5 (CH₃); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 223 (Found: C, 48.15; H, 4.00; N, 18.61. Calcd. for C₉H₉N₃O₄: C, 48.43; H, 4.03; N, 18.83%).

2-Amino-5-(4-benzoyloxy-3-methoxy)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4j): Brown needles, m.p. 87–89 °C, mol. wt. 295.2; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 3361 (NH), 3045 (ArC–H), 2863 (alipC–H), 2815 (OCH₃), 1760 (C=O), 1609 (C=N–N=C), 1069 (C–O–C), 915, 835, 820 (subs. aromatic); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 8.75 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.83 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.46–7.70 (5H, m, Ar-H), 3.11 (3H, s, OCH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 210 (CO), 171.8 (Oxadiazole C₂), 149.4 (Oxadiazole C₅), 159.1 (Ar–C₃), 144.5 (Ar–C₁), 136.6 (Ar–C'₁), 131.3 (Ar–C'₄), 129.1 (Ar–C₅), 128.1 (Ar–C'₂), 128.1 (Ar–C'₃), 128.1 (Ar–C'₅), 128.1 (Ar–C'₆), 120.3 (Ar–C₄), 118.6 (Ar–C₆), 111.9 (Ar–C₂), 52.3 (OCH₃); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 295 (Found: C, 64.88; H, 4.27; N, 14.15. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃N₃O₃: C, 65.08; H, 4.40; N, 14.23%).

2-Amino-5-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4k): Dark yellow needles, m.p. 97–98 °C, mol. wt. 230.2; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 3330 (NH), 3065 (ArC–H), 1605 (C=N–N=C), 1430 (C=C), 1060 (C–O–C), 815, 795 (subs. aromatic), 732 (Ar-Cl); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 8.17 (1H, s, NH), 7.50 (1H, m, Ar-H), 6.75 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 171.3 (Oxadiazole C₂), 150.2 (Oxadiazole C₅), 141.0 (Ar–C₁), 134.4 (Ar–C₂), 134.1 (Ar–C₆), 128.6 (Ar–C₄), 126.7 (Ar–C₃), 126.7 (Ar–C₅); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 230 (Found: C, 41.19; H, 2.02; N, 18.01; Cl, 30.59. Calcd. for C₈H₅N₃OCl₂: C, 41.73; H, 2.17; N, 18.26; Cl, 30.86%).

2-Amino-5-(3,5-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4l): Dark brown needles, m.p. 92–93 °C, mol. wt. 281.2; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 3330 (NH), 3065 (ArC–H), 1607 (C=N–N=C), 1430 (C=C), 1062 (C–O–C), 815, 795 (subs.

aromatic), 735 (Ar-Cl); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 8.76 (3H, s, Ar-H), 8.17 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 171.3 (Oxadiazole C₂), 150.4 (Oxadiazole C₅), 142.6 (Ar–C₁), 135.9 (Ar–C₃), 135.9 (Ar–C₅), 124.9 (Ar–C₆), 124.9 (Ar–C₂), 127.6 (Ar–C₄); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 281 (Found: C, 56.19; H, 5.52; N, 5.30. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅N₃O₅: C, 56.91; H, 5.92; N, 5.53%).

2-Amino-5-(5-bromo-4,6-dimethoxy)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4m): Brown needles, m.p. 85–87 °C, mol. wt. 230.2; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 3244 (NH), 2927 (ArC–H), 2865 (alipC–H), 2815 (OCH₃), 1611 (C=N–N=C), 1070 (C–O–C), 915, 830, 810, 610 (subs. aromatic), 715 (Ar-Br); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 7.75 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.25 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.52 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 3.10 and 3.23 (6H, s, OCH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 172.1 (Oxadiazole C₂), 150.3 (Oxadiazole C₅), 149.9 (Ar–C₆), 127.4 (Ar–C₂), 116.3 (Ar–C₃), 108.4 (Ar–C₁), 94.3 (Ar–C₅), 54.7 (OCH₃); MS (EI, 70 eV), *m/z* 281 (Found: C, 42.46; H, 2.38; N, 14.79; Br, 27.95. Calcd. for C₁₀H₇N₃O₂Br: C, 42.70; H, 2.49; N, 14.95; Br, 28.11%).

Screening for antimicrobial activity:

All the synthesized compounds were tested for their antimicrobial activity by adopting the experimental method of Benson^{35,36}. Whatman No. 1 filter paper discs of 6 mm diameter, placed in a Petri dish, were autoclaved. The test compounds in measured quantities (1.0 mg, 0.5 mg) were dissolved in 5 mL dimethylformamide to produce 200 ppm and 100 ppm solutions respectively. The filter paper discs were allowed to dry and the amount of the substance per disc was taken as 500 and 250 μ g. The bacterial (24 h) and fungal (48 h) cultures from the slants were diluted with sterile water and mixed thoroughly to prepare a clear homogeneous suspension. These suspensions were uniformly spread on solidified agar (nutrient and potato dextrose agar) medium. The filter paper discs prepared from dimethylformamide medium were carefully placed over the spreaded cultures and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h for bacteria and at 28–30 °C for 48 h for fungi. Paper discs treated with dimethylformamide alone served as control. After the incubation period the plates were examined for inhibition zones. The diameters of inhibition zones (including the diameter of the disc) were measured. All determinations were made in triplicate for

each of the compounds and the average value was taken. The antibacterial and antifungal screening results were presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activity of compounds **4a-m** was studied against the growth of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escheri-*

chia coli, (Gram-negative) and *Bacillus subtilis*, *Streptococcus aureus* (Gram-positive) organisms at the three concentrations (25, 50 and 100 ppm) taking Streptomycin as the standard (Table 2). The majority of the compounds exhibited significant (good) antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *K. pneumonia*, *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* as com-

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of compounds **4a-m**

Compd.	Zone of inhibition (mm)											
	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ($\mu\text{g disc}^{-1}$)			<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ($\mu\text{g disc}^{-1}$)			<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> ($\mu\text{g disc}^{-1}$)			<i>Streptococcus aureus</i> ($\mu\text{g disc}^{-1}$)		
	25	50	100	25	50	100	25	50	100	25	50	100
4a	0	4	8	2	5	7	0	4	6	0	5	8
4b	0	4	7	0	3	8	0	3	7	0	2	6
4c	0	5	8	0	4	8	0	4	9	1	5	9
4d	2	5	9	0	4	9	0	5	10	0	3	9
4e	2	4	10	0	5	9	2	6	10	1	5	9
4f	0	5	9	0	4	8	2	4	7	1	4	8
4g	0	2	4	0	0	5	0	2	4	0	2	5
4h	0	6	12	0	5	9	2	7	12	0	5	11
4i	0	5	8	0	4	8	0	3	7	0	5	8
4j	0	5	9	0	4	8	0	6	10	1	5	9
4k	2	8	13	2	7	11	0	7	12	2	6	11
4l	0	7	12	2	8	12	0	8	12	2	6	11
4m	0	7	11	2	6	10	0	7	10	0	6	11
Streptomycin	0	8	12	2	7	10	2	8	12	2	7	11

Table 3. Antifungal activity of the compounds **4a-4m**

Compd.	Zone of inhibition (mm)											
	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> ($\mu\text{g disc}^{-1}$)			<i>Pellicularia solmanicolor</i> ($\mu\text{g disc}^{-1}$)			<i>Cryosporium pannical</i> ($\mu\text{g disc}^{-1}$)			<i>Candida albicans</i> ($\mu\text{g disc}^{-1}$)		
	25	50	100	25	50	100	25	50	100	25	50	100
4a	0	2	7	0	0	5	0	3	6	0	2	7
4b	0	2	6	0	0	6	0	0	5	0	2	6
4c	0	4	7	0	0	4	0	2	5	0	3	7
4d	0	7	11	0	5	10	0	5	10	2	8	11
4e	0	6	10	0	5	9	0	4	8	0	5	9
4f	0	6	10	0	3	8	0	4	8	0	5	9
4g	2	4	7	0	5	8	1	3	6	2	4	6
4h	2	8	12	0	6	11	2	6	10	2	7	12
4i	0	5	9	0	5	8	0	6	9	0	5	10
4j	2	6	10	0	5	9	0	5	10	0	4	8
4k	2	7	11	0	8	12	0	7	12	0	6	10
4l	0	8	12	2	7	11	0	8	13	0	5	11
4m	2	8	13	2	8	12	2	8	12	2	7	11
Griseovulvin	0	8	12	2	7	10	2	8	12	2	7	11

pared to Streptomycin. The screening results of antibacterial activity revealed that compounds **4k** and **4l** exhibited greater while compounds **4h** and **4m** exhibited approximately similar activity to the standard Streptomycin. Compounds **4d**, **4e** and **4f** exhibited slightly less antibacterial activity. Remaining compounds exhibited weak to high antibacterial activity against all bacterial strains used for our evaluation.

Antifungal activity :

The compounds **4a-m** was also screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *C. pannical* species along with the standard fungicide Griseofulvins **4a-m** (Table 3). The disc diffusion method was followed for screening the compounds at three concentrations (25, 50 and 100 ppm). The screening results revealed that all the compounds displayed good antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *C. pannical*. However, compounds **4h**, **4k**, **4l** and **4m** showed high antifungal activity when compared with the Griseofulvins.

The antimicrobial activity of the compounds varied upon the type and position of the substituents at 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety. It can be concluded from the antimicrobial screening results that when 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were substituted with aryl halide the antimicrobial activity was altered to an appreciable extent. The presence of chlorine is most effective among the halogens.

Conclusion :

In conclusion we have developed a convenient method for the synthesis of novel 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives in excellent yields which is not so easy to achieve by chemical methods. These compounds exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against the growth of bacterial and fungal strain. The antimicrobial activity of the compounds varied upon the type and position of the substituents at 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety. It is evident from the antimicrobial screening results that when 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were substituted with aryl halide the antimicrobial activity was altered to an appreciable extent. The presence of chlorine is most effective among the halogens.

Acknowledgement

The author sincerely thanks to UGC, New Delhi for the financial assistance and Analytical Instrumentation Centre, Chandigarh for recording spectra and microanalyses.

References

1. F. A. Omar, N. M. Mahfouz and M. A. Rahman, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1996, **31**, 819.
2. S. M. Golovlyova, Y. A. Moskvichev, E. M. Alov, D. B. Kobylinsky and V. V. Ermolaeva, *Chem. Heterocycl. Compd.*, 2001, **37**, 1102.
3. F. Liu, B. Wang and Z. Zhang, *Youji Huaxue*, 2001, **21**, 1126.
4. A. Hetzheim and K. Moeckel, *Adv. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1967, **7**, 183.
5. J. Hill, in : K. T. Potts, (eds.), "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1984, Vol. 6, p. 427.
6. X. Wang, Z. Li and J. Yang, *Synth. Commun.*, 2002, **32**, 1097.
7. L. K. Sharma, S. Kumar, P. Yadav and R. K. P. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2008, **47**, 1277.
8. S. Kumar, L. K. Sharma and R. K. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 1160.
9. S. Kumar, S. Singh and R. K. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 1041.
10. A. A. El-Emam, O. A. Al-Deeb and M. Al-Omar, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**, 5107.
11. B. S. Holla, R. Gonaslaves and S. Shenoy, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **35**, 267.
12. A. O. Maslat, M. Abussaud, H. Tashtoush and M. Al-Talib, *Pol. J. Pharmacol.*, 2002, **54**, 55.
13. Z. Xiajuan, Z. Zhang and G. Jin, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2002, **5**, 228.
14. X.-J. Zou, L.-H. Lai, G.-Y. Jin and Z.-X. Zhang, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2002, **50**, 3757.
15. S. G. Kucukguzel, E. E. Oruc, S. Rollas, F. Sahin and A. Ozbek, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **37**, 197.
16. D. Chauhan, J. S. Chauhan, J. Singh, S. K. Bajpai and M. N. Joshi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2003, **42**, 215.
17. P. R. Kagthara, N. S. Shah, R. K. Doshi and H. H. Parekh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1999, **38**, 572.
18. R. K. Preethi, S. S. Niraj, K. D. Rajeev and H. H. Parekh, *Heterocycl. Commun.*, 1998, **4**, 561.
19. T. P. Mohan, B. Vishalakshi, K. S. Bhat and G. N. Kendappa, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 1798.
20. D. A. Kennedy and L. A. Summers, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1981, **18**, 401.
21. M. Santagati, M. Modica, A. Santagati, F. Russo, A. Caruso and V. Cutuli, *Pharmazie*, 1994, **49**, 880.

22. M. D. Mullican, M. W. Wilsonj, D. T. Connor, C. R. Kostlan, D. J. Schrier and R. D. Dyer, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1993, **36**, 1090.
23. H. I. Yale and K. Losee, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 478.
24. M. S. Khan, R. M. Khan and S. Drabu, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2001, **11**, 119.
25. J. Maillard, M. Vincent, R. Morin and M. Bernard, French Pat. M379 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, **57**, 15251g).
26. K. A. Jessen, N. M. English, J. Y. Wang, S. K. Maliartenou, S. P. Archer and L. Qiu, *Mol. Cancer Ther.*, 2005, **4**, 761.
27. A. A. Farghaly, A. A. Bekhit and J. Y. Park, *Arch. Pharm.*, 2000, **333**, 53.
28. F. T. Cappel, K. A. Evans, T. L. Graybill and G. Burton, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 3257.
29. S. Kumar and R. K. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 934.
30. S. Kumar, L. K. Sharma and R. K. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 1129.
31. S. Kumar, S. Singh and R. K. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **87**, 1145.
32. C. K. Mann and K. K. Barnes, "Electrochemical Reactions in Non-aqueous Systems", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1970.
33. A. J. Fry, "Synthetic Organic Electrochemistry", Wiley-Interscience Publication, New York, 1989, pp. 71-78.
34. T. Shono, "Electroorganic Synthesis", Academic Press Ltd., London, 1991, pp. 11-19.
35. H. J. Benson, "Microbiological Applications", 5th ed., W. C. Brown Publications, MA, Boston, 1990, p. 134.
36. C. A. Winter, E. A. Risley and G. W. Nuss, *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.*, 1962, **111**, 544.